

The Principles Underlying Aromatic Side-chain Reactivity from the Standpoint of the Electronic Theory of Valency.

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1. *Historical: Principles of Correlation and Inversion.*

Recent work on the effect of nuclear substituents on reactions in the side-chains of benzene derivatives has led to generalisations which pave the way to a theory of aromatic side-chain reactivity closely linked with the modern theory of nuclear aromatic substitution.

Some time ago Olivier demonstrated the existence of a relation between nuclear and side-chain reactivity, for the example of the latter represented by the acid hydrolysis of benzene chlorides (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1922, **41**, 301, 646 ; 1923, **42**, 516, 775): the velocities of hydrolysis for three isomers of the form $R \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot CH_2Cl$ were found to be in the order $o, p > m'$ or $m > o, p$, according as R belonged to the *op*- or *m*-orienting series ; and, moreover, the facilitating or retarding action of different groups R exhibited a close parallelism to their influence on reactivity in ordinary nuclear substitution. Similar relationships have since been established for several other side-chain transformations, including the condensations of benzyl chlorides with benzene in the presence of aluminium chloride, the saponification of benzoic esters, the addition of hydrogen sulphide to benzonitriles, and bromination in a methyl side-chain (Olivier and Berger, *ibid.*, 1926, **45**, 710 ; 1927, **46**, 605 ; Kindler, *Annalen*, 1926, **450**, 1 ; Ingold and Rothstein, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 1217).

It is known, however, that there is another group of side-chain reactions for which the above relations become to a large extent inverted. Lapworth, Shoesmith and others have found (*J. Chem.*

Soc., 1922, 1391 ; 1924, 1312, 2278 ; 1926, 214) that the two groups of nuclear substituents for which the ease of acid hydrolysis of isomeric benzyl halides are respectively in the order $o, p > m$ and $m > o, p$, become interchanged (with the exception of chlorine and bromine—see Section 6) when the reaction studied is the reduction of benzyl bromides with hydriodic acids ; indications of a similar phenomenon are apparent in the work of Franzen and Rosenberg (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1920, *ii*, 101, 333) on the alkaline alcoholysis of benzyl halides ; and Tasman has shown (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1927, **46**, 658) that the effect of different nuclear substituents on the velocity of alkaline hydrolysis of phthalides runs antiparallel to their influence on reactivity in the side-chain transformations mentioned in the preceding paragraph. A further clear illustration is available in the work of Conant, Kirner and Hussey (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **47**, 448), and especially in that of Bennett and Berry (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1676) on the conversion of benzyl chlorides into corresponding iodides. Obviously the two groups of side-chain reactions are in some fundamental respect the inverse of each other, and this circumstance is of course, at the basis of the successful application by Lapworth and Shoesmith of the principles of alternate polarities to most of the examples studied by them.

2. - Classification of Side-chain Reactions.

The view here under development incorporates the above analogies and conclusions, and starts from the classification of side-chain transformations given by Ingold and Rothstein (*Ann. Reports, Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **24**, 155 ; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 1217). These reactions are divided into two main categories according to whether (type A) an *influx* of electrons from the nucleus towards the side-chain, or (type B) a *recession* of electrons from the side-chain towards the nucleus, facilitates the change. The influx of electrons which assists reactions of type A may be required either to liberate or partly liberate a portion of the side-chain which carries all its electrons with it (type A₁) or to attract towards the side-chain an electron-seeking reagent (type A₂). Similarly, the electron-recession which facilitates reactions of type B may assist either the partial or complete liberation of a group which abandons a previously shared electron-pair (type B₁), or the electrostriction of a basic (positive-centre-seeking) reagent (type B₂). The following table contains some examples.

Type.	Example.	Facilitated process.
A ₁	Thermal fission of benzylammonium hydroxides...	$\text{Ph} \rightarrow \text{CH}_2 \text{---} \overset{\curvearrowright}{\text{NR}_2^{\oplus}}$
"	Acid hydrolysis of benzyl chloride ...	... $\text{Ph} \rightarrow \text{CH}_2 \text{---} \overset{\curvearrowright}{\text{Cl}}$
"	Addition of H ₂ S to benzonitrile ...	... $\text{Ph} \rightarrow \text{C} \equiv \overset{\curvearrowright}{\text{N}}$
A ₂	Side-chain bromination of toluene ...	... $\text{Ph} \rightarrow \text{CH}_2 \text{.....} \overset{\delta+\delta-}{\text{Br.Br}}$
B ₁	Reduction of benzyl bromide by HI ...	... $\text{Ph} \leftarrow \overset{\curvearrowleft}{\text{CH}_2} \text{---} \text{Br} \dots \text{I.H}$
B ₂	Alkaline alcoholysis of benzyl chloride	... $\text{Ph} \leftarrow \text{CH}_2 \text{Cl} \text{.....} \overset{\ominus}{\text{OEt}}$
"	Conversion of benzyl chloride into iodide	... $\text{Ph} \leftarrow \text{CH}_2 \text{Cl} \text{.....} \overset{\ominus}{\text{I}}$

It should be stated that, in the absence of data relating to the influence of nuclear substitution of velocity, the preliminary assignment of a side-chain reaction to its proper class is one of the main practical difficulties in the application of the theory, and that although an analysis of the circumstances of the reaction and of the type of reactivity normally characteristic of the aromatic compound and reagent is always valuable as a guide, it frequently fails to do more than indicate a probable allocation. In general, two separate points require consideration: first, a decision is required between two alternative possible mechanisms, which are usually related much as are those of the second and sixth of the above examples; secondly, it must be decided which phase of the actual mechanism controls the speed, although naturally, if intermediate forms are not present in appreciable concentration, the rate-controlling phase is necessarily the initial one. The utility in connection with this part of the problem, of data relating to the influence of nuclear substitution on side-chain reactivity can immediately be made apparent without reference to the less superficial points which arise in the adaptation of the theory of nuclear aromatic substitution to side-chain reactions. Facilitation by a uniquely electron-repelling group (*e. g.*, *p*-Me) and retardation by a uniquely electron-attracting group (*e. g.*, *p*-NO₂) is diagnostic of reactions of type A, whilst the inverse of these effects characterises reactions of type B. Furthermore, it is possible to detect complications due to simultaneous membership of both types,—a condition which may arise from two

main causes: either the side-chain reaction may proceed by two contemporaneous mechanisms, one belonging to each type, or its single route may involve two rate-affecting phases, one of each type. If there are two simultaneous reactions the speeds corresponding with a series of nuclear substituents taken in order of decreasing electron-release and increasing electron-restraint should pass through a single minimum," because at both extremes of the series the acceleration of one mechanism will mask the retardation of the other; possible examples of this effect are provided by Franzen and Rosenberg's experiments and by Berger and Olivier's investigation of the hydrolysis of benzoyl chlorides (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1927, 46, 516; compare *Ann. Reports, Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 24, 157). If a single mechanism requires both electron-absorption and release, the velocities should pass through a single maximum, since at both ends of the series the retardation of one phase will mask the acceleration of the other; it has been suggested (*Ann. Reports, Chem. Soc.* 1928, 25, 147), on the basis of Lapworth and Manske's investigations (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2533) that such conditions obtain in the formation of cyanohydrins from benzaldehydes. The matter is considered further in Section 7.

3. Reactions Requiring Electron-release.

A transformation having been assigned to type A, the modern theory of ordinary nuclear benzene substitution (for summary see *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1929, 48, 799), in which it is implicit that the substituting agents require available electrons at the focus of reaction, may be applied. Adaptation is necessary, however, in order to allow for the circumstance that the effects of nuclear substituents have to traverse not only the nucleus, but also part of the side-chain in order to reach the region of reaction. It may be recalled that Ingold and Shaw (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2918) have shown how the electron-availability at a nuclear carbon atom in a monosubstituted benzene is modified by (a) the nature, and (b) the orientation, of the substituent. As to (a),—groups were divided into four categories according to their electron-affinities relatively to that of the hydrogen atom they replace, and according to whether or not the groups possess unshared valency electrons, the presence of which would enable negative charges to appear in the nucleus as a result of tautomeric transformation. As to (b),—it was found, when the

mode of propagation of effects originating in these causes was considered, that whereas the permanent electron-affinity of the group increases or decreases the electron-availability of the *o*- and *p*-carbon atom strongly, and affects the *m*-carbon atoms in the same sense but to a smaller extent (inductive effect, $\pm I$), the existence of a mechanism whereby an electromeric charge-transfer can occur when stimulated by an electron-demanding reagent augments the effective electron-availability of the *o*- and *p*-carbon atoms, but is without sensible effect on the *m*-carbon atoms (tautomeric effect, $+T$). The following table of examples is intended to facilitate the application of these principles. The special modification which it is necessary to introduce in applying them to side-chain reactions of type A are two-fold. First, owing to the small displaceability of the electrons in a single linking, selectively heavy damping accompanies the transmission of the tautomeric effect through side-chain single-linkings to the point of reaction (compare Goss, Ingold and Wilson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2443; also *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1929, 48, 804). Secondly, for a reason explained below, the tautomeric effects should, with additional damping in the nucleus, affect reactivity in *m*-side-chains.

Classification A of Nuclear Substituents.

($+I$, $op \rightarrow m$ -activation. $-I$, $op \rightarrow m$ -de-activation.
 $+T$, op -activation).

Group No.	Mechanism.	Examples.
1.	$+I$ $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \leftarrow R \\ \leftarrow R \end{array} \right.$	$\cdot Me$, $\cdot CMe_3$
2.	$-I$ $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \rightarrow R \\ \rightarrow R \end{array} \right.$	$\cdot CO_2H$, $\cdot COMe$, $\cdot SO_2R$, $\cdot NO_2$, $\oplus NMe_3$
3.	$-I + T$ $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \rightarrow R \\ \rightarrow R \end{array} \right.$	$\cdot OMe$, $\cdot Hals$, $\cdot NO$, $\cdot SOR$, $\oplus SMe_2$, $\oplus IPh$
4.	$-I - T$ $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \leftarrow R \\ \leftarrow R \end{array} \right.$	$\cdot CR:CR'R'$, $\ominus O$

A comprehensive exemplification of this part of the general theory, which, it will be seen, incorporates the equivalent of Olivier's correlation principle, can be found in the work of Olivier, Berger, Kindler, Lapworth, Shoesmith and others already referred to (Section 1), and detailed allusion may be omitted. Further consideration may, however, appropriately be given to the two special circumstances (above) which complicate the analogy between nuclear and side-chain reactivity, since these determine the limitations affecting

the validity of Olivier's correlation principle within the field to which it was intended to apply.

4. *Limitations of the Correlation Principle.*

The effect of selective damping in the side-chain may first be considered. In group 3 of the above classification of substituents, the inductive and tautomeric effects work in opposite directions, and everything depends, therefore, on the relative importance, so far at least as concerns *op*-nuclear reactivity and type-A reactivity in *op*-side-chains. The inductive effect results in de-activation, to an extent depending on the electron-affinity of the group; the tautomeric effect leads to activation, in proportion to the tendency of the unshared electrons to become shared, that is, to the basicity of the group. Now the electron-affinity of the halogens in the neutral state is pronounced (compare stability of the halide ions), but iodine differs from the others in possessing considerable basicity (compare stability of iodonium ions); and in nuclear substitution (nitration) it has been found (Ingold and Shaw, *loc. cit.*) that, for iodine, the tautomeric effect predominates, this element belonging to the *op*-activating section of the group-3 substituents, whilst, for the other halogens, the inductive effect has main importance, and these belong to the de-activating series. In type-A side-chain reactions, on the other hand, the tautomeric effect of iodine, presumably owing to selective damping, no longer outweighs the inductive, and this element ranges itself with the other halogens as a de-activating substituent. It will be seen that the iodine substituent qualitatively violates Olivier's correlation principle, and that the broader theory naturally accommodates the apparent anomaly.

Before exemplifying tautomeric polar influence on reactivity in a *m*-side-chain, a few words of explanation are desirable with regard to the theoretical inference that such effects should be perceptible. It will be readily understood how, in nuclear substitution, in which the reagent normally has the choice of exciting and thereafter utilising, the tautomeric effect in those positions (*o*- and *p*-) in which they are primarily, and hence most easily, stimulated, the orientation process is largely self-definitive,—the reagent becoming more and more irrevocably committed to *o*- or *p*-attack during its approach, from the moment when it began to exert electrical action on the aromatic molecule until union is definitely accomplished; thus it is that the

+*T*-effect (unlike the +*I*-effect which is a permanent property of the aromatic molecule) never leads to appreciable *m*-substitution. On the other hand, a reagent attacking a *m*-side-chain has no alternative method of utilising an existing mechanism for tautomeric electron displacement within the nucleus than that of allowing the final stages of transmission of the effect of such displacements to proceed to the point of reaction by ordinary induction; and thus a substituent should, by its tautomeric, as well as by its inductive, effect, influence reactivity in *m*-side-chains, although naturally to a less degree than were the side-chains otherwise situated. It is possible to perceive the operation of this principle in several recorded observations on side-chain reactions, but all are rendered more or less complicated by the simultaneous presence of the inductive effect, the relay of which to the *m*-position is not peculiar to side-chain reactions. In the experimental part of this paper, however, we show that a *m*-phenyl substituent appreciably increases the speed of acid hydrolysis of benzyl bromide. Now phenyl (a form of substituted vinyl) is a substituent of group 4 in the above classification, but its inductive effect is negligibly small; in diphenyl itself it is not merely small, but is zero, both from symmetry and from the determined zero dipole moment of this hydrocarbon. The strong *op*-orienting action of phenyl is, of course, a manifestation of its tautomeric effect. Therefore, since in the phenyl-substituted benzyl bromide the tautomeric effect alone is under observation, the experiments referred to definitely confirm the anticipated cause of failure here considered of the simple analogy with nuclear substitution.

5. *Reactions Requiring Electron-restraint.*

For side-chain reactions known to belong to type B, the procedure corresponding to that described above, utilises, not the analogy of ordinary nuclear substitution, that is, the replacement of nuclear hydrogen by the action of negative-centre-seeking reagents, but the analogy furnished by aromatic substitution reactions in which the replacement of electro-negative elements such as chlorine is effected by the attack of positive-centre-seeking (basic) reagents. The theory of this kind of aromatic substitution has not yet been greatly developed, but it has been outlined (Ingold, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1929, 48, 809); and the main features are, first, that the manifestations of the

inductive effect become reversed in sign, $+I$ representing de-activation and $-I$, activation, although their nuclear distribution, $op > m$, remains as before; and second, that whilst the tautomeric effect $+T$ is not stimulated by the reagents now under consideration an op -activating tautomeric effect $-T$, depending on $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturation in the orienting substituent, is rendered operative by such reagents, since this structural feature permits the appearance in the nucleus of positive charges by electromeric transfer. This scheme of classification, which is illustrated in the table below, will also apply to side-chain reactions of type B, after introduction of qualifications, similar to those mentioned in section 3, relating to the diminished relative importance of the tautomeric effect, and the ability of this effect to penetrate a m -side-chain.

Classification B of Nuclear Substituents.

($+I$, $op > m$ -de-activating. $+I$, $op > m$ -activating.
 $-T$, op -activating.)

Group No.	Mechanism.	Examples.
1.	$+I$	Me, CMe_3 , O^-
2.	$-I$	Hals., NMe_3
3.	$-I-T$	CO_2H , NO , NO_2 , CN .
4.	$+I-T$	$\text{CR}:\text{CR}'\text{R}''$.

On comparing this scheme with that mentioned in Section 3, it becomes evident that, owing to the radically altered nature of the tautomeric effect, the influence of groups on the kind of nuclear substitution now considered is far from being uniformly the inverse of their influence on reactivity in the replacement of nuclear hydrogen. On the other hand, in side-chain transformations, the diminished importance of the tautomeric effect leads to a certain simplification of the theory, inasmuch as it renders the modifying influence of groups on type-B reactivity more nearly the uniform inverse of their effect on reactivity in changes of type-A. In short, a fairly consistent inversion of the kind indicated is to be expected, and it is on this basis that the theory accommodates the series of relations formerly elucidated by the principle of alternate polarities. Ample illustration of this matter is to be found in the

work of Oliver, Tasman, Lapworth, Shoesmith, Conant, Bennett and others already mentioned (Section 1); at the present stage more interest attaches to expected departures from exact inversion. This is discussed in the next Section, but it is appropriate to mention here that the appended experimental record contains a proof, on similar lines to those indicated in Section 4, that the kind of tautomeric effect which is specially characteristic of side-chain reaction of type B, can influence reactivity in a *m*-side-chain.

6. *Limitations of the Inversion Principle.*

Failure of the inversion rule is to be expected amongst groups which are associated with a powerful tautomeric (or weak inductive) effect, and at the same time fulfil one of two conditions relating to classification. These conditions are (1) that the group shall belong to group 3 of classification A and also to either of groups 2 or 3 of classification B, and (2) that it shall belong to either of groups 1 or 4 of the A-classification, and also to group 4 of the B-classification.

An illustration is furnished by the anomalous behaviour of chlorine and bromine mentioned in Section 1. These substituents fulfil the first of the above alternative classificatory conditions since they belong to group 3 of the type-A scheme, and group 2 of the type-B scheme. In nuclear substitution they are in the peculiar position of being de-activating but *op*-orienting; that is, their inductive effect ($-I$) depresses reactivity throughout the nucleus, the *m*-positions included, whilst their tautomeric effect ($+T$) restores activity to the *op*-positions only, raising them above the standard of reactivity set by the de-activated *m*-position (*op*-orientation) but not up to the standard represented by unsubstituted benzene (de-activation). In the acid hydrolysis of the chloro- and bromo-benzyl bromides (type-A reaction) these phenomena qualitatively repeat themselves: the substituted compounds are all hydrolysed more slowly than benzyl bromide, but the isomerides amongst themselves stand in the order $op > m$ as regards their rates of reaction. Turning to the reduction of these compounds (type-B reaction), the tautomeric effect ($+T$) of the nuclear substituents should be inoperative and their inductive effect ($-I$) should activate in all positions in the normal order, $op > m$; and this is what happens. In short, when the substituted compounds are compared with the unsubstituted parent the inversion rule holds, but when the substituted

isomerides are compared amongst themselves the inversion rule fails. The anomaly, although inconsistent with any simple alternating principle, is thus naturally accommodated by the view here developed.

In the appended experimental record will be found an instance illustrating the even more complete failure of the inversion principle. The nuclear substituent was chosen to fulfil the second of the two alternative classificatory conditions, and in selecting it we had in mind, not only the further theoretical requirement that its inductive effect should be relatively small, but also the practical one that it should be inert towards the reagents employed. The latter condition ruled out many forms of the substituted vinyl group which otherwise would have been suitable. On the other hand, phenyl is a group which possesses the necessary stability and has the added advantage that its inductive effect is entirely negligible. The influence of the nuclear phenyl substituent on certain side-chain transformations was therefore investigated, and following precedent, we utilised the acid hydrolysis of benzyl bromides as representative of side-chain reactions of type-A, whilst reduction of the same compounds with hydriodic acid served to exemplify the reactions of type-B. We are able to show, first that the introduction of a phenyl group into either the *m*- or *p*-position of benzyl bromide enhances both the velocity of hydrolysis and that of reduction, and secondly, that, as regards the relative reactivities of isomerides, the *m*- and *p*-compounds retain the same order, namely $p > m$, for both reactions. The inversion principle thus fails on both counts, and it is clear that, as theoretically anticipated, whilst the phenyl group has the ability to generate tautomeric electron-displacements in either sense, the direction of the displacements actually stimulated in a given case depend on the necessities of the attacking reagent. Incidentally it may be noted that this is exactly the result which is needed to reconcile the observed effects of phenyl in another field of investigation, in which it has found that this group can excite mobility in attached tautomeric systems, not only when the displaceable atom is released as a cation (*e.g.*, H,—"prototropy") but also when it migrates as an anion (*e.g.* Br,—"anionotropy"); these observations necessitate the assumption of electron-absorption or-release by phenyl according to the electrical requirements of the kind of tautomerism involved (Burton, Ingold and Shoppee, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 904, 1950; 1929, 447, 1199).

7. *Reactions Requiring Electron-absorption and Release.*

It is necessary to refer once more to the classification of side-chain reactions which forms the starting point of the considerations here presented. The classification assumed that side-chain reactions depend on a preliminary dissociation or association, in the course of which an electric charge, appearing in the side-chain, leads to consequential electrical adjustments as between the side-chain, the nucleus and any substituents attached thereto. When several aromatic nuclei possess a common side-chain a counterpart to these assumed, transient dissociations can be found in directly demonstrable ionic equilibria in which the charged components have considerable life (*e.g.*, $\text{Ph}_3\text{C}\cdot\text{K}$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{C}\cdot\text{Cl}$ in ionising solvents); but, under the same structural conditions, another type of dissociation also becomes directly observable, in which the separable components apparently bear no charge (*i.e.*, $\text{Ph}_6\text{C}_2 \rightleftharpoons 2\text{Ph}_3\text{C}$ in non-ionising solvents). A theory of side-chain reactivity obviously cannot be general unless it includes recognition of this type of dissociation also, not only when it is pronounced as in the chemistry of free radicals, but also in any of its more ephemeral manifestations, should these arise in other circumstances. The conditions leading to the stability of free radicals have been considered by Burton and Ingold (*Proc. Leeds Phil. Soc.*, 1929, 1, 421) whose conclusions, in so far as they affect the question under discussion, may be summarised as follows: The side-chain of a free radical, although neutral, may be regarded as initially unsaturated, with respect to both negative and positive electricity, because it requires to gain or lose an electron in order to complete its duplets (achieve spin-symmetry), and to lose or gain an electronic charge in order to recover the neutrality which the completion of the duplets would destroy. Now if this interpretation of the electrostatic condition of free radicals is correct, then the essential condition for promoting dissociation into neutral components is the possibility of duplex electrical re-adjustments; and if this actually is the case, a general provision for side-chain reactions depending on such a mechanism has already been made (although not hitherto explicitly) in the foregoing statement of the theory, inasmuch as reactions have been envisaged which are characterised by the inclusion within a single mechanism of "phases" (which need not necessarily be stages in the sense implying separation in time) respectively

dependent on electron-absorption and release. Some justification for contemplating such a category of side-reactions is to be found in the fact that the inferred practical criterion relating to the effect of nuclear substituents has been experimentally encountered (Section 2) but the investigation referred to did not include a study of the phenyl substituent, the duplex tautomeric effect of which should place it in a highly peculiar position with respect to such reactions. In this conclusion one may perceive a reason why the sufficient accumulation of phenyl, or other aryl groups possessing a common side-chain constitutes almost the only known structural condition for the realisation of considerable dissociation into neutral components; furthermore the obvious corollary that the introduction of phenyl substituents into any positions (but especially into the *o*- or *p*-positions) of the aromatic nuclei bearing the side-chain should increase such dissociation is confirmed, so far as substitution in the *p*-position is concerned by Schlenk's well-known work on free radicals containing the *p*-diphenyl group. Apart from the *p*-diphenyl, however, other polynuclear aryl groups are known markedly to facilitate dissociation into radicals, and since the order of the relative intensities with which they do so is also known, a simple test of the whole matter can be made.

The work of Schlenk and Gomberg and their collaborators (*Annalen*, 1910, 372, 1; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 1652; 1922, 44, 1829) establishes the sequence—

for the ability of these groups to promote dissociation into neutral radicals. If this sequence is to be interpreted as representing capacity for the duplex electrical readjustments referred to above, then the same series should represent in addition, firstly, the order in which the groups facilitate side-chain reactions involving dissociations dependent on electron-release (reactions of sub-type A_1), and secondly, the relative facilitation by the groups of side-chain transformations dependent on dissociations demanding electron-restraint (reactions of sub-type B_1). The reactions we have studied belong respectively to these sub-types; and for both reactions we find a sequence identical with the above:

It is scarcely necessary to add that completeness is not claimed

for theoretical treatment here outlined. In particular, separate discussion is required regarding two other structural influences, namely, those due to external molecular electric fields, and to steric factors, which become of considerable importance in certain cases of *o*-substitution.

EXPERIMENTAL.

1. Preparation of Aryl Methyl Bromides.

3-Bromomethyldiphenyl.—3-Methyldiphenyl was prepared by a method identical in principle with that of Perrier (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1892, [3], 7, 181) and purified by alternate fractionation (column) and freezing. Bromination was effected by leading dry bromine (10% excess) into the hydrocarbon at 200° (bath temperature) and fractionating the product. The pale yellow oil, b.p. 150°/15 mm., consisted essentially of 3-bromomethyldiphenyl contaminated by an inert impurity not containing side-chain bromine. Therefore, as preliminary to the quantitative work described below, the percentage purity of each sample was determined by treatment with alcoholic trimethylamine and estimation of the ionic bromine thus formed. *m*-Phenylbenzyltrimethylammonium picrate, obtained by addition of aqueous sodium picrate to a solution of the quaternary ammonium bromide prepared in this way, separated from aqueous alcohol in rhombic plates, m.p. 152°. (Found: C, 58.2; H, 4.79. $C_{22}H_{22}O_7N_4$ requires C, 58.15; H, 4.85 per cent.)

4-Bromomethyldiphenyl.—4-Methyldiphenyl was prepared (compare Carnelly, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1876, 29, 18), purified, and brominated as in the former example, and the bromination product fractionated. The portion, b.p. 130-140°/10 mm., which solidified on cooling, yielded 4-bromomethyldiphenyl as pearly leaflets, m.p. 82°, on crystallising from a mixture of ether and ligroin below 0°. (Found: C, 63.3; H, 4.36. $C_{13}H_{11}Br$ requires C, 63.2; H, 4.45 per cent.). The substance gave the theoretical proportion of bromide ion when treated with trimethylamine by the method illustrated for the *m*-compound and the quaternary ammonium bromide solution, when treated with aqueous sodium picrate, yielded *p*-phenylbenzyltrimethylammonium picrate, which crystallised from aqueous alcohol, in rhombic plates, m.p. 179°. (Found: C, 57.9; H, 5.11.

$C_{22}H_{22}O_7N_4$ requires C, 58.15; H, 4.85 per cent.). The less volatile portion of the bromination product on crystallisation from alcohol, with use of charcoal, yielded a yellow microcrystalline powder, m.p. 129°. Analysis showed this to be a *dibromo-4-methyldiphenyl*. (Found: C, 48.0; H, 3.82. $C_{13}H_{10}Br_2$ requires C, 48.1; H, 3.07 per cent.). Except that its stability to boiling alcohol indicates that both bromine atoms are attached to the nucleus, there is no evidence of their orientation, but the most probable positions would appear to be the 2:4'-positions.

α-Bromomethylnaphthalene.—This was prepared as described by Schmidlin and Massini (*Ber.*, 1909, 42, 2389), but we confirm Shoesmith and Rubli's statement (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 3098) that it is a crystalline solid, m.p. 53°.

β-Bromomethylnaphthalene.—The compound, which had the properties recorded by Schultz (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 1529), was prepared by his method, except that the temperature during bromination was maintained at 200°.

2. Hydrolysis of Aryl Methyl Bromides.

General method.—Weighed quantities (about 0.08 g.) of the bromide, each dissolved in 100 c.c. of 90% aqueous alcohol, were kept in a thermostat at 24° for various measured periods of time and the liberated hydrobromic acid titrated with carbonate-free sodium hydroxide. Usually from 20-45% of the complete reaction was followed in this way, and the velocity coefficients were then calculated from each observation by means of the formula $k = (1/t) \times \log_{10} a/(a-x)$, the units of time being minutes.

Preliminary experiments with *β*-bromomethylnaphthalene in which the reaction was followed nearly to completion showed that its course substantially conforms to the unimolecular law although the calculated coefficients tends to fall slightly near the end of the process.

Results.—These are summarised in the following table, in which the second set of determinations relating to *β*-bromomethylnaphthalene is included to show that the disturbance associated with the "tail" of the reaction is without influence on the velocity coefficients recorded for the first 20-45% of hydrolysis, since, even

if as much as 80% of the change is followed, the mean coefficient remains substantially the same:—

Substance hydrolysed.	Number of observations.	Percentage of reaction followed.	Calc. $k \times 10^4$		
			Mini- mum.	Maxi- mum.	Mean.
Benzyl bromide	3	20.7	76	79	78
3-Bromomethyl- diphenyl.	6	34.3	138	154	146
4-Bromomethyl- diphenyl.	8	37.5	158	173	165
β -Bromomethyl- naphthalene.	5	45.8	170	192	184
"	10	81.5	177	195	185
α -Bromomethyl- naphthalene.	6	40.7	208	227	220

The relative values of the coefficients obtained for α - and β -bromomethylnaphthalene are consistent with Shoemith and Rubli's observations on these substances (*loc. cit.*).

3 Reduction of Aryl Methyl Bromides.

General Method.—(a) Weighed quantities of each bromide (about 0.15 g.) were reduced for 1 or 2 hours at 100° in 10 c.c. of a solution prepared from constant-boiling hydriodic acid (1 vol.) and glacial acetic acid (10 vols.), and the liberated iodine estimated as usual. Simultaneously with each experiment a control was performed in which all conditions were maintained the same, except for the omission of the bromide, the object being to eliminate error arising from the liberation of iodine by atmospheric attack.

(b) Weighed quantities (about 0.3 g.) of those bromides which were found to be reduced nearly completely under the conditions of method (a) were each reduced at 86° for 6 or 15 hours with 10 c.c. of a solution prepared by making 1 vol. of constant-boiling hydriodic acid up to 5 vols. with glacial acetic acid. The remainder of the experiment, and the controls, were carried out as above.

Results.—These are recorded in the following table, the footnote to which illustrates the degree of consistency of individual experiments.

Substance reduced.	Percentage reduction.			
	Method (a)		Method (b)	
	1 hour.	2 hours.	6 hours.	15 hours.
Benzyl bromide	—	32*	—	—
3-Bromomethyl-diphenyl.	26	48	—	—
4-Bromomethyl-diphenyl	36	67	—	—
β -Bromomethyl-naphthalene.	95	99	23	41
α -Bromomethyl naphthalene.	96	99	35	50

* (Individual values : 32, 34, 30, 30.5 %).

The results for the bromomethylnaphthalenes are not in good agreement with those obtained by Shoesmith and Rubli (*loc. cit.*).

Summary.

A theory of aromatic side-chain reactivity, linking this subject on the one hand with nuclear aromatic substitution and on the other with pure radical chemistry, is advanced and supported by observations on the reactivity in hydrogen and reduction of polynuclear analogues of benzyl bromide.

One of us (C. S. P.) desires here to acknowledge his indebtedness to the Government of H. H. the Maharaja Gaekwar of Baroda for granting to him a period of study-leave during which this investigation has been carried out.

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Received November 18, 1929.